

Experimental speed-of-sound data and a fundamental equation of state for normal hydrogen optimized for flow measurements

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ABSTRACT

Speed-of-sound measurements for normal hydrogen (*n*-hydrogen) in a temperature range between 273 K and 323 K were carried out using a cylindrical resonator at pressures from 1 MPa to 10 MPa and a dual-path pulse-echo system at pressures from 20 MPa to 100 MPa. The relative expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$) of the measurements range from 0.04 % to 0.08 %. Based on these measurements and data from the literature, a fundamental equation of state (EOS) was developed for the calculation of thermodynamic properties of *n*-hydrogen. It is expressed in terms of the Helmholtz energy with the independent variables temperature and density. Due to the fundamental nature of the Helmholtz energy, the equation can be used to calculate all thermodynamic properties from one mathematical expression. In contrast to typical EOS of this kind, the boundary conditions are somewhat more restricted. The relevant temperature and pressure ranges are limited to typical pipeline and storage conditions of gaseous hydrogen, including temperatures relevant for measurements with critical nozzles (140 K to 370 K with pressures up to 100 MPa). The computational speed for the implementation of the correlation in measurement sensors plays a superior role. Therefore, the equation is kept as short as possible, and exponents are of integer-kind. Most of the experimental data are still reproduced within their measurement uncertainties.

1. Introduction

Over the past decades, the excessive consumption of fossil fuels has led to negative long-term effects on local, regional, and global scales. Prominent effects are the impact on public health due to air pollution, environmental impact due to global climate change, direct destruction of the environment, and energy source shortages as the depletion of fossil fuel reserves proceeds much faster than their natural regeneration [1,2]. Therefore, alternate solutions are required, which demand more environmentally friendly and sustainable technologies. One promising solution is the use of hydrogen to replace fossil fuels. So far, the use of hydrogen has been mostly limited to industrial processes as raw material but is expected to become a significant clean energy vector in the future. However, due to insufficient infrastructure, large-scale use of hydrogen is not yet possible. To overcome this issue, thermophysical properties of normal hydrogen (*n*-hydrogen) [3] of metrological quality are required. The term “normal” is used for the hydrogen configuration at ambient

temperature, namely the mixture of 75 % orthohydrogen and 25 % parahydrogen, the two nuclear spin isomers of hydrogen. The equilibrium composition is a temperature dependent property. The percentage of parahydrogen increases at lower temperatures, e.g., 28.5 % at around 150 K, 50.4 % at around 77 K, and more than 99.8 % below 20 K [4]. However, the conversion from ortho- to parahydrogen without the use of catalysts can take days or even months [5]. Therefore, thermophysical properties of *n*-hydrogen can be measured at lower temperatures and even in the liquid region with suitable experimental procedures.

Numerous measures and investments have been made throughout the world to support a structural change toward a sustainable economy. One is known as the European Green Deal [6], which was launched in 2019. Within its framework, the EMPIR 20IND11 MetHyInfra project [3] addresses hydrogen flow metrology. An objective is the assessment and calibration of flow meters for the measurement of hydrogen flow under typical pipeline and storage conditions of gaseous hydrogen, whereby the lower temperature limit results from the requirements of

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Table 1

Description of the gas samples used for the speed-of-sound experiments. x denotes mole fraction.

Gas	CAS Number	Supplier	Purity x	Purification method
Hydrogen	1333-74-0	BOC	0.999995 ^a	None
Nitrogen	7727-37-9	BOC	0.999995 ^b	None
Helium	7440-59-7	BOC	0.99999 ^c	None

^a Impurities (stated by supplier): $x(\text{N}_2) \leq 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \leq 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{O}_2) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{CO}) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{CO}_2) \leq 0.5 \times 10^{-6}$, and $x(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$.

^b Impurities (stated by supplier): $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{O}_2) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{H}_2) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $[x(\text{CO}) + x(\text{CO}_2)] \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, and $x(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y) \leq 0.5 \times 10^{-6}$.

^c Impurities (stated by supplier): $x(\text{N}_2) \leq 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \leq 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{O}_2) \leq 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{H}_2) \leq 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $x(\text{CO}_2) \leq 0.5 \times 10^{-6}$, and $x(\text{C}_x\text{H}_y) \leq 0.5 \times 10^{-6}$.

volume- and mass-flow measurements with critical nozzles (140 K to 370 K with pressures up to 100 MPa). For the modelling of the processes and applications, accurate predictions of the thermodynamic properties of n -hydrogen are required. The state of the art is the use of empirical multiparameter fundamental equations of state (EOS). The current reference EOS for n -hydrogen was developed by Leachman et al. [7] in 2009. At that time, speed-of-sound measurements were provided at limited temperature and pressure ranges, not covering the region of interest addressed here. The speed of sound is both a caloric and thermal property, directly related to properties such as density, isobaric heat capacity, and isothermal compressibility, which can be measured with high accuracy. Consequently, using speed-of-sound data for the development of equations of state can significantly improve their quality and help verify the other properties [8,9]. Furthermore, in the application of critical flow Venturi nozzles for metrology, speed of sound is a quantity of primary interest. Therefore, new speed-of-sound data were measured

Table 2

Uncertainty budget for the speed of sound in n -hydrogen at a pressure of $p = 5.020$ MPa and a temperature of $T = 273.153$ K. $w_{0,\text{EOS}}$ is the calculated speed of sound at calibration conditions in helium, Δt_0 is the time difference at calibration conditions, α is the mean thermal expansion coefficient over the interval $[T_0, T]$, β is the isothermal compressibility at measurement conditions, and Δt is the time difference at measurement conditions.

Quantity	Value	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution
f_{200}	21714.24 Hz	0.01 Hz	0.060 m	0.001 m·s ⁻¹
T	273.139 K	0.015 K	$2.906 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	0.000 m·s ⁻¹
p	5.000 MPa	0.03 MPa	$0.215 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{MPa}^{-1}$	0.006 m·s ⁻¹
η	$8.43 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$	$3.37 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$	$2.731 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$	0.009 m·s ⁻¹
λ	$0.179 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	$7.16 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	$0.819 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$	0.006 m·s ⁻¹
γ	1.419	0.014	$0.705 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.010 m·s ⁻¹
ρ	$4.303 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$	$0.233 \text{ m}^4 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$	0.000 m·s ⁻¹
w_{EOS}	$1304.291 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	$0.096 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.082	0.014 m·s ⁻¹
f_1	39,500 Hz	1 Hz	$3.03 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}$	0.000 m·s ⁻¹
C	$3.04 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$	$8.71 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ m} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$	$4.55 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1} \cdot \text{Pa}$	0.040 m·s ⁻¹
L	$5.9981 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ m}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}$	21627 s^{-1}	0.255 m·s ⁻¹
Combined expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of w : $0.52 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$				

Table 3

Uncertainty budget for speed of sound in n -hydrogen at a pressure of $p = 60.010$ MPa and a temperature of $T = 273.162$ K. $w_{0,\text{EOS}}$ is the calculated speed of sound at calibration conditions in nitrogen, Δt_0 is the time difference at calibration conditions, α is the mean thermal expansion coefficient over the interval $[T_0, T]$, β is the isothermal compressibility at measurement conditions, and Δt is the time difference at measurement conditions.

Quantity	Value	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution
$w_{0,\text{EOS}}$	$707.34 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	$0.0707 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	2.550	0.180 m·s ⁻¹
Δt_0	27.8421 μs	0.001 μs	$64.792 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \mu\text{s}^{-1}$	0.065 m·s ⁻¹
T_0	298.152 K	0.015 K	$0.069 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	0.001 m·s ⁻¹
p_0	69.96 MPa	0.03 MPa	$1.433 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{MPa}^{-1}$	0.041 m·s ⁻¹
α	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K}^{-1}$	$4.508 \cdot 10^4 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}$	0.008 m·s ⁻¹
β	$9.47 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$	$9.47 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$	$5.983 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{MPa}$	0.001 m·s ⁻¹
Δt	10.9170 μs	0.0024 μs	$165.23 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \mu\text{s}^{-1}$	0.393 m·s ⁻¹
T	273.162 K	0.015 K	$0.1538 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	0.002 m·s ⁻¹
p	60.01 MPa	0.03 MPa	$2.4848 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{MPa}^{-1}$	0.072 m·s ⁻¹
Combined expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of w : $0.89 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$				

within the temperature region of interest. Ideally, the new measurements would have extended over a broader temperature range and this may be something to address in future work. Additionally, a new EOS was developed within the scope of this work. It should be noted that the new EOS aims at the specific requirements in the EMPIR 20IND11 MethHyInfra project [3]. The EOS will be applied in computational methodologies, where the iterative calculation time during simulations needs to be considered. For instance, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations require calculations of the thermodynamic properties on every grid point in each time step [10]. Therefore, its functional form is kept as simple as possible and consists of polynomial terms only. This was possible because the region of interest is far away from the critical regime ($T_{c,\text{H}_2} = 33.145$ K vs. $T_{\text{min,EOS}} = 140$ K). Additionally, only integer temperature and density exponents are used in order to reduce the computation time.

2. Speed-of-sound measurements

The speed of sound in hydrogen is the highest of any technically relevant gases, which in turn means that measurements are demanding and must be carried out with great care. When using a steady-state technique (e.g., a resonator), the high speed of sound leads to high resonance frequencies of the gas. As the speed of sound in pure hydrogen increases with pressure, measurements at high pressure become challenging as the resonance frequency of the gas might overlap with the resonances of the resonator shell. On the other hand, transient techniques can only be applied if the acoustic impedance of the fluid (equal to the product of density and speed of sound) is high enough, otherwise it is impossible to obtain distinct ultrasonic pulses. Therefore, speed-of-sound measurements were performed in n -hydrogen using a cylindrical resonator at low pressures of 1 MPa to 10 MPa and a dual-path pulse-echo technique at higher pressures from 20 MPa to 100 MPa. Both sets of

Table 4

Speed of sound w measured in gaseous n -hydrogen and expanded uncertainties $U(w)$ ($k = 2$) at given temperatures T and pressures p , including the relative expanded uncertainties $U(w)/w$. The measurements were performed using a cylindrical resonator (CR) at pressures from 1 MPa to 10 MPa and the dual-path pulse-echo technique (DPPE) at 20 MPa to 100 MPa.^a

T K	p MPa	w m·s ⁻¹	$U(w)$ m·s ⁻¹	100· $U(w)/w$ -	T K	p MPa	w m·s ⁻¹	$U(w)$ m·s ⁻¹	100· $U(w)/w$ -
CR ^b					DPPE ^c				
273.139	1.01	1268.74	0.50	0.04	298.151	19.97	1486.68	1.25	0.08
273.140	2.00	1277.48	0.50	0.04	298.153	30.09	1577.09	1.00	0.06
273.138	3.01	1286.28	0.51	0.04	298.153	40.07	1663.77	0.94	0.06
273.139	4.00	1295.06	0.51	0.04	298.153	49.98	1748.00	0.89	0.05
273.139	5.00	1303.90	0.52	0.04	298.153	59.98	1828.85	0.88	0.05
273.141	6.00	1312.91	0.52	0.04	298.153	70.06	1909.55	0.91	0.05
273.140	7.01	1321.94	0.53	0.04	298.154	80.07	1986.83	0.92	0.05
273.139	8.01	1330.87	0.53	0.04	298.153	89.96	2060.02	0.96	0.05
273.141	9.00	1339.82	0.55	0.04	298.153	99.60	2128.99	0.98	0.05
273.139	10.00	1348.87	0.56	0.04	CR ^b				
DPPE ^c					CR ^b				
273.163	20.03	1442.49	1.13	0.08	323.150	1.01	1374.98	0.51	0.04
273.164	30.03	1535.15	0.95	0.06	323.152	2.01	1383.17	0.50	0.04
273.162	40.04	1627.75	0.90	0.06	323.151	3.00	1391.33	0.51	0.04
273.163	50.00	1717.01	0.88	0.05	323.152	4.01	1399.52	0.51	0.04
273.162	60.01	1803.89	0.89	0.05	323.150	5.00	1407.64	0.52	0.04
273.162	70.06	1887.41	0.91	0.05	323.150	5.97	1415.56	0.53	0.04
273.162	79.97	1967.30	0.90	0.05	323.151	7.00	1423.96	0.53	0.04
273.165	89.84	2043.76	0.93	0.05	323.152	8.00	1432.06	0.54	0.04
273.162	99.48	2114.64	0.96	0.05	323.151	9.00	1440.17	0.55	0.04
CR ^b					DPPE ^c				
298.153	0.98	1322.65	0.50	0.04	323.152	19.98	1533.40	1.28	0.08
298.153	1.98	1331.08	0.50	0.04	323.154	30.05	1616.46	1.15	0.07
298.150	2.98	1339.53	0.51	0.04	323.154	40.03	1699.39	1.36	0.08
298.150	4.00	1348.30	0.52	0.04	323.151	50.03	1781.43	1.26	0.07
298.151	5.00	1356.80	0.53	0.04	323.153	60.02	1859.54	0.99	0.05
298.152	5.97	1365.26	0.54	0.04	323.155	69.92	1934.51	1.17	0.06
298.150	6.97	1373.82	0.55	0.04	323.155	80.04	2010.25	1.15	0.06
298.152	8.00	1382.50	0.57	0.04	323.155	90.05	2079.92	1.22	0.06
298.151	9.00	1391.31	0.58	0.04	323.152	99.49	2145.05	1.23	0.06
298.151	10.00	1399.87	0.60	0.04					

^a Standard uncertainties are $u(T) = 0.015$ K and $u(p) = 0.03$ MPa.

^b Measurement frequency range 21 kHz to 24 kHz.

^c Measurement frequency 5 MHz.

Fig. 1. Speed of sound measured in n -hydrogen as a function of pressure along three isotherms. Lines are shown to visualize the course of the isotherms.

measurements were conducted at temperatures of 273 K, 298 K, and 323 K. Gases used in this work are described in Table 1. For calibration of the cylindrical resonator, helium was used while, for the dual-path pulse-echo system, calibration was performed with nitrogen.

2.1. Cylindrical resonator

In order to determine the speed of sound at pressures below 10 MPa, a cylindrical resonator was used. The resonator was based on the design of Ruffine and Trusler [11] and the underlying analysis model was discussed in detail by Demirdezen et al. [12]. The cylindrical resonator was fabricated from aluminum. It consists of a cylindrical cavity of 60 mm nominal length, 15 mm internal diameter and 25 mm external diameter, which was closed at both ends with transducer end plates. The transducers had the same external and internal diameter as the cavity, a length of 10 mm and they closed the cavity with a plane diaphragm of a thickness of 1.5 mm. More details on the assembly of the resonator are discussed by Demirdezen et al. [12]. Both diaphragms were equipped with ceramic piezoelectric disc transducers (Piezo technologies, type K360, thickness 0.4 mm, diameter 10 mm) bonded to the center of the diaphragm with a thin film of epoxy resin to form a bimorph transducer. One of these transducers was connected through a hermetically sealed feedthrough to a function generator (Agilent, model 33220A) and was driven by an ac signal to create a sound source. The second transducer was connected through a second feedthrough to a lock-in amplifier (Stanford Research Systems, model SRS830), allowing for the detection of the phase and the amplitude of the received signal from the acoustic

Table 5
Fluid-specific properties of *n*-hydrogen and the universal gas constant.

Property	Formula sign	Unit	Value for the EOS of Leachman et al. [7]	Value for the present EOS	Reference
Critical temperature	T_c	K	33.145	33.145	Leachman et al. [7]
Critical density	ρ_c	mol·dm ⁻³	15.508	15.508	Leachman et al. [7]
Molar mass	M	g·mol ⁻¹	2.01588	2.01588	Wieser & Berglund [32]
Molar gas constant	R	J·mol ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹	8.314472	8.314462618	Mohr & Taylor [33] Tiesinga et al. [34]

Table 6
Parameters of the reduced ideal isobaric heat capacity of this work according to Eq. (15). The reducing parameters R , T_c , and ρ_c are given in Table 5.

i	n_i	t_i^*
1	0.47292	1
2	-0.0383891	2
3	7.85228×10^{-4}	3
4	2.3685×10^{-5}	4
5	-3.59134×10^{-8}	6

Table 7
Parameters of the residual part of the reduced Helmholtz energy according to Eq. (16). The reducing parameters R , T_c , and ρ_c are given in Table 5.

k	n_k	t_k	d_k
1	-0.00468246	-1	1
2	0.39649	0	1
3	-1.134	1	1
4	-0.358687	2	1
5	-0.0010302	-1	2
6	0.0492408	0	2
7	-0.5728	1	3
8	-9.30404×10^{-5}	0	4
9	0.00485964	1	4

pressure wave within the cavity. By changing the driving frequency at a constant sinusoidal drive voltage of 20 V_{p-p}, the resonance frequency f_{200} of the second longitudinal mode of the gas-filled cavity was measured. This resonance frequency is related to the speed of sound w in the gas as follows:

Table 8

Test values for computer implementation. The input variables are temperature T and density ρ , and the test values are calculated for pressure p , molar isobaric heat capacity c_p , speed of sound w , enthalpy h , entropy s , and Helmholtz energy a .

T K	ρ mol·dm ⁻³	p MPa	c_p J·mol ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹	w m·s ⁻¹	h J·mol ⁻¹	s J·mol ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹	a J·mol ⁻¹
200	0.2	0.333 314	27.294 812	1 092.668 06	-2 772.264 0	-21.174 930	-203.849 865
200	20	47.622 241	29.474 265	1 620.836 34	-2 383.813 8	-63.684 938	7 972.061 79
300	0.2	0.500 318	28.931 627	1 322.156 79	57.764 984 1	-13.108 516	1 488.727 92
300	20	73.227 143	30.587 453	1 936.441 97	1 001.856 76	-55.174 534	13 892.859 9

Table 9

Average absolute relative deviation (AARD/%) of ideal isobaric heat-capacity data for *n*-hydrogen calculated with the short EOS developed in this work. The AARD is based on the number of data points in the region of interest (N_{reg} , 140 K $\leq T \leq$ 370 K). For comparison, the same data were evaluated with the reference EOS of Leachman et al. [7].

Author	N	N_{reg}	$T_{\text{min}} - T_{\text{max}}$ K	AARD (Leachman et al. [7]) %	AARD (this work) %
Colonna et al. (2012) [42]	90	6	5–10000	0.010	0.12
Haar et al. (1961) [43]	84	24	10–5013	0.011	0.10
Kosloff et al. (1974) [44]	60	2	100–6000	0.018	0.13
Popovas et al. (2016) [45]	60	7	5–20000	0.012	0.13
Woolley et al. (1948) [35]	84	24	10–5013	0.015	0.096
Zúñiga et al. (2021) [46]	18	4	5–600	0.010	0.11
Total	396	67	5–20,000		

$$w = (f_{200} - \Delta f_{v-t} - \Delta f_{\text{end}} - \Delta f_{\text{vib}})L \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta f_{v-t} = -0.5f_{200} \left[\left(1 + \frac{2b}{L} \right) (\gamma - 1) D_t^{0.5} + D_v^{0.5} \right] / \sqrt{\pi f_{200} b^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta f_{\text{end}} = \frac{-\rho w_{\text{EOS}}^2 (C/L) f_{200}}{1 - (f_{200}/f_1)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta f_{\text{vib}} = f_{200} \left[\sqrt{\frac{\gamma(c_v - c_{\text{vib}})}{c_p - c_{\text{vib}}}} - 1 \right] \quad (4)$$

Correction terms for the visco-thermal boundary layers at the inner walls of the cavity Δf_{v-t} , non-rigidity of the transducers Δf_{end} , and vibrational relaxation of the fluid Δf_{vib} were considered. Here, L is the length of the cavity, b is the radius of the transducers, γ is the ratio of the specific isobaric heat capacity c_p to the specific isochoric heat capacity c_v of the fluid, ρ is the density of the fluid, C is the mean static compliance of the transducers, f_1 is the fundamental resonance frequency of the transducers, and c_{vib} is the vibrational contribution to the specific heat capacity of the fluid. The thermal diffusivity is $D_t = \lambda/(\rho c_p)$ and the viscous diffusivity is $D_v = \eta/\rho$, where λ is the thermal conductivity and η the dynamic viscosity. The thermodynamic properties c_p , c_v , w_{EOS} , and ρ were calculated with the EOS by Ortiz Vega et al. [13] for the calibration in helium and by Leachman et al. [7] for *n*-hydrogen as implemented in REFPROP 10.0 [14,15]. The transport properties λ and η were calculated with correlations by Hands and Arp [16] and Arp et al. [17] for Helium and by Assael et al. [18] and Muzny et al. [19] for *n*-hydrogen, respectively, as implemented in REFPROP 10.0 [14,15]. c_{vib} was calculated for

n -hydrogen from the Planck-Einstein equation with a characteristic vibrational temperature of 6323 K [20]; however, this term is negligible under the conditions of interest here. For monoatomic helium, the vibrational contribution is $c_{\text{vib}} = 0$. To determine f_1 , a short acoustic coupler ($L = 6$ mm) was used instead of the cavity and the resonance spectrum was recorded in ambient air and at vacuum. L and C were determined from calibration measurements in helium [12]. The calibration was conducted at pressures of 1 MPa and 10 MPa for each temperature individually; thus, no temperature correction was necessary.

The resonator was mounted inside a pressure vessel, rated for pressures up to 400 MPa. The pressure was adjusted with a manual syringe pump connected to the pressure vessel and measured by a pressure transducer (Keller, model 33X, 100 MPa full scale). To control the temperature, the pressure vessel was completely immersed in a temperature-controlled bath (Fluke, model 6020). A platinum resistance thermometer (Fluke, model 5615) connected to a resistance read-out device (Fluke, model 1502A) was inserted into an axial thermowell in the pressure vessel and used to measure the temperature of the vessel.

Before the n -hydrogen sample investigated was fed into the system, five filling-evacuation cycles with n -hydrogen were performed to purge the system of impurities. Therefore, the pressure vessel, the syringe pump, and the external tubing were filled with n -hydrogen up to a pressure of 10 MPa and subsequently exhausted to vacuum.

The standard uncertainties of the thermodynamic and transport properties were used as reported in the literature cited above. The standard uncertainties in the measurement of temperature and pressure are 0.015 K and 0.03 MPa, respectively. For f_{200} , the standard uncertainty is 0.01 Hz. For the estimation of the standard uncertainties of the calibration quantities, details can be found in Demirdezen et al. [12]. The influence of c_{vib} on the measurements was insignificantly small and conducted uncertainty calculations have shown that the associated uncertainty is negligible and was not considered here. The standard uncertainty of the speed-of-sound measurements in n -hydrogen was determined according to:

$$u(w) = \left[\left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial f_{200}} \right) u(f_{200}) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \eta} \right) u(\eta) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \lambda} \right) u(\lambda) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \rho} \right) u(\rho) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial w_{\text{EOS}}} \right) u(w_{\text{EOS}}) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \gamma} \right) u(\gamma) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial f_1} \right) u(f_1) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial C} \right) u(C) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial L} \right) u(L) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial T} \right) u(T) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial p} \right) u(p) \right)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

Exemplarily, a detailed description of the uncertainty budget for the speed-of-sound measurement at $p = 5$ MPa and $T = 273$ K is shown in Table 2. The expanded uncertainty was calculated considering a coverage factor of $k = 2$.

2.2. Dual-path pulse-echo apparatus

The dual-path pulse-echo technique is very well established for measurements of the speed of sound in the liquid phase [21–23] but can also be used for measurements in the gas phase if the acoustic impedance of the gas is high enough [24–26]. The measurement setup used in this

work was already applied for measurements in liquid n -pentane [27] and recently in gaseous helium [26]. Wedler and Trusler [26] have shown that the system is capable of measuring the speed of sound in helium, a gas with a high speed of sound and a low acoustic impedance, with an expanded relative uncertainty from 0.03 % to 0.04 %. As they described the setup in detail, the system and the measurement procedure are only briefly outlined here.

The apparatus consisted of a cylindrical ultrasonic cell made from Invar 36 nickel–iron alloy, in which a ceramic piezoelectric disc transducer was mounted perpendicular to the axis of the cell (same model as for the resonator). The transducer was located off-center in the axial direction to ensure different distances from the transducer to the two ends of the cylindrical cell. A three-cycle sinusoidal tone burst, generated by a function generator (Agilent, model 33220A), was used to excite the transducer. The tone burst had a carrier frequency of 5 MHz and an amplitude of 20 V_{p-p}. The resulting sound waves propagated in the two different axial directions of the cell. At both ends, the cell was closed by plane reflectors. The sound waves reflected from the ends were received by the piezoelectric disc transducer and captured by a digital oscilloscope (Agilent, model DSO3012A). Due to the different path lengths, a time difference Δt existed between the returning echoes. The difference of the path lengths $\Delta L = (L_2 - L_1)$ was known from calibration experiments in nitrogen at $T_0 = 298.15$ K and $p_0 = 70$ MPa as described by Wedler and Trusler [26]. The speed of sound in nitrogen was calculated from the EOS of Span et al. [28]. The speed of sound in the hydrogen gas was then determined according to:

$$w = \frac{2(L_2 - L_1)}{\Delta t + \tau_{\text{dif}}} \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) includes a small diffraction correction τ_{dif} which depends on the speed of sound, considering the path length, the wavelength, and the effective diameter of the transducer [29]. The influence of temperature and pressure differences between the calibration measurements and the measurement in n -hydrogen on ΔL was accounted for by considering the mean thermal expansion α and the compressibility β of the Invar alloy. Details on this can be found in Wedler and Trusler [26]. The system was

designed such that the same pressure vessel was used for the both the pulse-echo cell and the acoustic resonator. The procedures for measurement and control of pressure and temperature were also the same and the same filling-evacuation procedure as described in section 2.2 was used.

To determine the uncertainty of the speed-of-sound measurements, the path length difference was eliminated in favor of the speed of sound w_0 in nitrogen at calibration pressure p_0 and temperature T_0 as well as the corresponding time difference Δt_0 . The standard uncertainty of the speed of sound was determined according to:

Fig. 2. Isobaric heat capacity of the ideal gas calculated from the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] and the new EOS as a function of temperature from a) 0 K to 1000 K and b) 140 K to 370 K, and c) percentage deviations of the ideal isobaric heat-capacity data calculated from the EOS as a function of temperature from 0 K to 600 K. The new EOS is presented as solid curves and the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] is presented as dash-dotted curves.

$$u(w) = \left[\left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial w_{\text{EOS},0}} \right) u(w_{\text{EOS},0}) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial T_0} \right) u(T_0) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial p_0} \right) u(p_0) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \Delta t_0} \right) u(\Delta t_0) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \Delta t} \right) u(\Delta t) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \alpha} \right) u(\alpha) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \beta} \right) u(\beta) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial T} \right) u(T) \right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial p} \right) u(p) \right)^2 \right]^{0.5}. \quad (7)$$

For reasons of simplicity, Eq. (7) neglects the uncertainty of the diffraction correction. In relative terms, the magnitude of that correction is $\leq 0.03\%$ and hence we assumed that the corresponding uncertainty contribution is negligible.

The standard uncertainty of the EOS for nitrogen was estimated by Span et al. [28] to be 0.6% at calibration conditions. However, this was a highly conservative estimation made in the absence of experimental data at high pressure. Meier and Kabelac [30] measured the speed of sound in nitrogen along six isotherms at temperatures between 275 K and 400 K with pressures up to 100 MPa. Compared with the EOS of Span et al. [28], their data exhibit a maximum absolute relative deviation (MARD) of 0.02%. Costa Gomes and Trusler [31] also measured the speed of sound in nitrogen along four isotherms at temperatures between 250 K and 350 K with pressures up to 30 MPa. Compared with the EOS of Span et al. [28] their data also exhibit a MARD of 0.02%. These results show the uncertainty of the EOS is generally much lower than the conservative estimate of Span et al. [28]. At a temperature of 300 K, which is close to our calibration temperature, both Costa Gomes and Trusler [31] and Meier and Kabelac [30] observed deviations from the EOS within $\pm 0.01\%$, and hence we take 0.01% as the standard relative uncertainty of the EOS at the calibration point. The standard uncertainty of the time differences was estimated according to an amplitude-dependent approach described by Wedler and Trusler [26]. For compressibility and thermal expansion, relative standard uncertainties were assumed to be 1% and 10% respectively, as described by Scholz et al. [27]. Exemplarily, a detailed description of the uncertainty budget for the speed-of-sound measurement at $p = 60$ MPa and $T = 273$ K is shown in Table 3. The expanded uncertainty was calculated considering a coverage factor of $k = 2$.

2.3. Results

The speed-of-sound measurements in n -hydrogen were conducted at temperatures of 273 K, 298 K, and 323 K at pressures up to 100 MPa. The measured data points are listed in Table 4 with the respective temperatures, pressures, and expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$). The data points are grouped into isotherms and the two measurement methods cylindrical resonator (CR) and dual-path pulse-echo (DPPE). In addition, the measured speed-of-sound data are plotted as a function of pressure in Fig. 1.

3. The Helmholtz-energy equation of state

The present EOS is explicit in terms of the Helmholtz energy a as a function of temperature T and density ρ . For the sake of simplicity, it is reduced with the temperature and the universal gas constant R . The independent variables are also used in their dimensionless form. Following the principle of corresponding states, the critical parameters are used for the reduction:

$$\frac{a(T, \rho)}{RT} = \alpha(\tau, \delta) \quad (8)$$

with

Table 10

Average absolute relative deviation (AARD/%) of experimental homogeneous density data for n -hydrogen calculated with the short EOS developed in this work. The AARD is based on the number of data points in the region of interest (N_{reg} , $140 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 370 \text{ K}$, $p \leq 100 \text{ MPa}$). For comparison, the same data were evaluated with the reference EOS of Leachman et al. [7].

Author	N	N_{reg}	$T_{\text{min}} - T_{\text{max}}$ K	$p_{\text{min}} - p_{\text{max}}$ MPa	AARD (Leachman et al. [7]) %	AARD (this work) %
Amagat (1893) [47]	73	16	273–321	0.1–304	0.50	0.63
Bartlett (1927) [48]	8	8	273.15	5.1–102	0.32	0.41
Bartlett et al. (1928) [49]	43	24	273–673	5.1–102	0.20	0.25
Bartlett et al. (1930) [50]	48	48	203–294	2.5–102	0.14	0.073
David & Hamann (1953) [51]	12	–	64–79	30.4–127	–	–
de Haas (1912) [52]	6	6	293.14	0.01–0.2	0.009	0.009
Holborn & Otto (1925) [53]	30	11	65–224	2.0–10.0	0.06	0.036
Holborn & Otto (1926) [54]	7	–	65–66	2.0–9.9	–	–
Jaeschke & Humphreys (1990), Gasunie [55]	68	68	273–354	0.2–26.3	0.008	0.008
Jaeschke & Humphreys (1990), Ruhrgas [55]	221	221	273–354	0.5–28.1	0.012	0.013
Jin et al. (1983) [56]	23	–	20–28	0.1–0.5	–	–
Johnston et al. (1953) [57]	227	41	33–300	0.5–20.9	0.075	0.10
Knaap et al. (1962) [58]	30	–	23–81	0.05–0.2	–	–
Liebenberg et al. (1977) [59]	1901	–	75–308	189–1984	–	–
Liebenberg et al. (1978) [60]	19	–	75–164	471–1871	–	–
Machado et al. (1988) [61]	60	38	130–160	1.2–106	2.0	1.9
Michels & Goudekot (1941) [62]	283	169	273–424	0.9–301	0.044	0.021
Michels et al. (1959) [63]	483	300	98–424	0.6–300	0.034	0.062
Presnall (1969) [64]	108	–	473–874	10.1–183	–	–
Sakoda et al. (2012) [65]	104	39	353–474	1.1–99.8	0.049	0.037
Scott (1929) [66]	18	18	298.14	0.1–17.2	0.058	0.082
Townend & Bhatt (1931) [67]	40	40	273–299	0.1–60.8	0.16	0.13
van Agt & Kamerlingh Onnes (1925) [68]	28	–	14–91	<0.01–0.2	–	–
van Itterbeek et al. (1966) [69]	161	–	21–41	0.3–16.1	–	–
Verschoye (1926) [70]	25	25	273–294	4.7–20.8	0.10	0.093
Wiebe & Gaddy (1938) [71]	47	33	273–574	2.5–102	0.058	0.025
Total	4073	1105	14–874	0.01–1984		

$$\tau = \frac{T_c}{T} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\delta = \frac{\rho}{\rho_c} \quad (10)$$

The required fluid-specific properties for the EOS of this work such as reducing parameters are listed in Table 5.

The Helmholtz energy is divided into an ideal (superscript o) and a residual (superscript r) contribution:

$$\frac{a(T, \rho)}{RT} = \alpha^o(T, \rho) + \alpha^r(\tau, \delta) \quad (11)$$

The ideal part is derived from the relation between the Helmholtz energy, internal energy u , and entropy s :

$$\alpha^o = u^o - Ts^o \quad (12)$$

The internal energy and the entropy are calculated with the isochoric heat capacity of the ideal gas c_v^o :

$$\alpha^o(T, \rho) = u_0^o - Ts_0^o + \int_{T_0}^T c_v^o dT - T \int_{T_0}^T \frac{c_v^o}{T^2} dT + RT \ln \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right) \quad (13)$$

There are only few literature data available for this property, so that the isobaric heat capacity of the ideal gas c_p^o is usually used as a basis and converted to the isochoric heat capacity via

$$c_v^o = c_p^o - R \quad (14)$$

For the ideal part, polynomial equations were adapted to the ideal isobaric heat capacity gas c_p^o calculated by Woolley et al. [35]. Literature research has identified more recent data for the vibrational modes of hydrogen, but the minimal changes in energy levels do not lead to significant changes in c_p^o . The ideal part was fitted according to the following equation:

$$\frac{c_p^o(\tau)}{R} = n_0^* + \sum_{i=1}^5 n_i \tau^{-i} \quad (15)$$

with $n_0^* = 1.61915$. Normally, n_0^* is the contribution of the translational and rotational energies of the molecules of n -hydrogen. However, since the equation is not valid at low temperatures, this empirical value was accepted here in order to better reproduce the isobaric heat-capacity data of the ideal gas despite using polynomial terms only. The coefficients n_i and temperature exponents t_i^* of the equation for the ideal-gas heat capacity are listed in Table 6.

The temperature exponents t_i^* are of integer-kind to increase the computational speed. To obtain a pure integer solution for the exponents of the polynomial terms when fitted to experimental data, special methods are required. In this work, the optimization problem was solved using the MATLAB-based fitter MFEOS [36,37]. The branch and bound algorithm of Kuipers [38] was applied to solve the integer problem and the relaxed sub-problems were solved using a sequential quadratic programming algorithm (SQP) available in MATLAB [37,39]. The thermodynamic properties were calculated using the open source library TREND 5.0 [40].

The residual part, also known as the real-gas contribution, is generally composed of four different term types: polynomial, exponential, Gaussian bell-shaped, and non-analytic terms. To increase the computational speed, only polynomial terms with temperature and density exponents of integer-kind are used in this work. The residual part of this work thereby reads

$$\alpha^r(\tau, \delta) = \sum_{k=1}^9 n_k \tau^k \delta^{d_k} \quad (16)$$

and the corresponding parameters are listed in Table 7.

Test values for computer implementation calculated with the thermodynamic software tool REFPROP 10.0 [14,15] are given in Table 8. The input variables are temperature T and density ρ , and the test values

Fig. 3. p,T-diagram illustrating the distribution of experimental homogeneous density data for *n*-hydrogen with the relation to the vapor pressure curve calculated with the EOS of Leachman et al. [7]. The region of interest for the present short EOS ($140 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 370 \text{ K}$, $p \leq 100 \text{ MPa}$) is marked in grey and shown separately on the bottom right. Data sets, which are (partly) located in this region are highlighted in green in the author list. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

are calculated for pressure p , molar isobaric heat capacity c_p , speed of sound w , enthalpy h , entropy s , and Helmholtz energy a . The number of digits of the test values is not related to the uncertainty of the model. Using the molar mass of hydrogen rounded to 4 decimals instead of the value given in Table 5 will affect the calculated speed of sound in the second decimal.

4. Comparison of the equation of state to experimental data

A literature research was carried out to set up an experimental database for thermodynamic properties of *n*-hydrogen, the frozen “normal” mixture of 25 % para- and 75 % orthohydrogen. Although the composition changes slowly with decreasing temperature, the data were reported by the authors to be *n*-hydrogen. The database includes homogeneous density, saturated liquid density, vapor pressure, speed-of-sound, isobaric heat-capacity, and thermal virial coefficient data. In addition to the experimental data, second virial coefficient determined with ab initio approaches from fundamental theories were used. Since the region of interest for the present short EOS (temperatures from 140 K to 370 K with pressures up to 100 MPa) is far away from the vapor–liquid equilibrium, vapor pressures and saturated liquid densities were not considered for the development of the present EOS and are, thus, not included in the evaluation. Moreover, the available literature data for

the isobaric heat capacity of the real gas (Gutsche [41]) pertain to temperatures below 40 K and hence do not cover the present region of interest. Therefore, only the speed-of-sound measurements presented in section 2, homogeneous densities, thermal virial coefficients, and isobaric heat capacities of the ideal gas were used to adjust the parameters of the short EOS. The statistical evaluation is carried out by means of percentage deviations of the measurements (index “DATA”) and calculated values from the EOS according to

$$\Delta x = 100 \frac{x_{\text{DATA}} - x_{\text{EOS}}}{x_{\text{DATA}}} \quad (17)$$

The average absolute relative deviation (AARD) is defined as

$$\text{AARD} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\Delta x_i|, \quad (18)$$

whereas the average absolute deviation (AAD) is calculated as

$$\text{AAD} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x_{i, \text{DATA}} - x_{i, \text{EOS}}|, \quad (19)$$

where N is the number of data points and x is a particular thermodynamic property.

Fig. 4. Percentage deviations of the experimental density data from the EOS as a function of pressure at selected temperatures ± 5 K. The plotted temperature and pressure range corresponds to the range of validity of the new EOS. The EOS of Leachman et al. [7] is presented as dash-dotted curves.

Fig. 5. Percentage deviations of the experimental density data from the EOS as a function of pressure of selected references. The plotted temperature and pressure range corresponds to the range of validity of the new EOS.

Table 11

Average absolute relative deviation (AARD/%) of experimental speed-of-sound data for *n*-hydrogen calculated with the short EOS developed in this work. The AARD is based on the number of data points in the region of interest (N_{reg} , $140 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 370 \text{ K}$, $p \leq 100 \text{ MPa}$). For comparison, the same data were evaluated with the reference EOS of Leachman et al. [7].

Author	N	N_{reg}	$T_{\text{min}} - T_{\text{max}}$ K	$p_{\text{min}} - p_{\text{max}}$ MPa	AARD (Leachman et al. [7]) %	AARD (this work) %
Carey et al. (1974) [72]	18	18	291–300	0.1–11.0	0.42	0.42
Giacobbe (1993) [73]	3	3	294–295	0.099	0.15	0.19
Güsewell et al. (1970) [74]	7	—	24–31	0.3–0.9	—	—
Hodge (1937) [75] ^a	11	11	273.15	0.1–10.1	5.2	5.2
Liebenberg et al. (1977) [59] ^b	1901	—	75–164	471–1871	—	—
Liebenberg et al. (1978) [60] ^b	10	—	75–164	473–1871	—	—
van Dael et al. (1965) [76]	212	—	18–34	<0.1–24.9	—	—
van Itterbeek et al. (1961) [77]	43	—	14–21	<0.1–0.2	—	—
van Itterbeek et al. (1963) [78]	111	—	15–21	0.1–23.1	—	—
This work	57	57	273–323	1–100	0.13	0.027
Total	2373	89	14–323	0.09–1871		

^a hydrogen reported with impurities, but of an unknown size.

^b partly in the solid region.

Fig. 6. Percentage deviations of the experimental speed-of-sound data from the EOS as a function of pressure. The plotted temperature corresponds to the range of validity of the new EOS. The plotted pressure corresponds to the range of the provided speed-of-sound data of previous publications.

4.1. Isobaric heat capacity of the ideal gas

For the development of the ideal part of the EOS, isobaric heat-capacity data of the ideal gas were used. Six data sets have been reported for *n*-hydrogen, cf. Table 9. The total number of data points (N), the data points for the region of interest (N_{reg}), the temperature range, and the AARD from the new EOS and the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] based on the region of interest are given.

In Fig. 2 a) and b), the ideal isobaric heat capacity calculated from the new EOS and the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] are illustrated as function of the temperature accompanied by the literature data [35,42–46]. Fig. 2 c) shows relative deviations of the ideal isobaric heat-capacity data from the new EOS as a function of temperature including the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] for comparison. The data have been computed with different methods, e.g., via ab initio energy levels obtained from a solution of the Schrödinger equation [44] or from energy levels derived from analysis of molecular spectra [35]. All data sets agree well with each other and are represented by the new EOS at

temperatures from 140 K to 370 K with AARDs from 0.096 % to 0.13 %, cf. Table 9. The AARDs of the data from the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] are smaller by one order of magnitude for most authors, showing the limits of an equation that consists purely of polynomial terms. Nevertheless, the accuracy within the region of interest is sufficient for this study. The maximum deviation of the data from the new EOS in the temperature range from 140 K to 540 K is 0.2 % and outside this region 1 % from 85 K to 650 K. These values are also the estimated uncertainty for calculated ideal isobaric heat capacities with the EOS. The new EOS exhibits unphysical behavior beyond these temperature ranges.

4.2. Homogeneous density

There are 4073 experimental homogeneous density data available in the literature, cf. Table 10. In Fig. 3, the distribution of the data is presented in a p,T -diagram covering temperatures from 14 K to 874 K with a maximum pressure of 1984 MPa, where the extreme pressures are already located in the solid-state region. The region aimed at in this

Fig. 7. Percentage deviations of the speed-of-sound data measured in this work with cylindrical resonator (CR) and dual-path pulse-echo (DPPE) from the new EOS as a function of the logarithmic pressure, including the experimental uncertainty. The EOS of Leachman et al. [7] is presented as dash-dotted curves.

work is marked in grey. Only data located in this region were considered for the development of the short EOS. These data sets are marked in green in Fig. 3 and are highlighted with bold letters in Table 10. The corresponding number of data points is separately listed for the region of interest (N_{reg}) and the AARD is based on this value instead of the overall number (N).

In Fig. 4, relative deviations of the experimental density data from the new EOS are shown as function of pressure at selected temperatures. The deviation of the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] from the new EOS is illustrated with dash-dotted curves. In the following, only the most important data sets for the validation of the EOS are discussed. The discussed data are presented separately in Fig. 5.

The measurements conducted by Jaeschke and Humphreys [55] in 1990 are deemed to be the most consistent and most accurate data and, thus, were used to fit the new EOS. They used two different measurement methods; therefore, the data are split into two data sets. The one referred to as Gasunie data [55] was measured with an optical interferometry apparatus with a given estimated combined uncertainty of $\pm 0.08\%$ ($k = 2$). The other, which is referred to as Ruhrgas data [55], was measured with a Burnett apparatus with an estimated combined uncertainty of $\pm 0.07\%$ ($k = 2$). The measurement series range from 273 K to 354 K with pressures up to 26.3 MPa (Gasunie [55]) and 28.1 MPa (Ruhrgas [55]). The Gasunie data [55] are represented with the new EOS with a maximum deviation of 0.03 % and an AARD of 0.008 %. The Ruhrgas data [55] are represented within 0.032 % and with an AARD of 0.013 %.

The data of Michels and Goudekot [62] from 1941 were chosen as reference at pressures from 30 MPa to 100 MPa at temperatures from 273 K to 373 K and the data of Michels et al. [63] from 1959 were chosen at temperatures down to 138 K. It should be noted that both data sets deviate from the data of Jaeschke and Humphreys [55] at pressures above 20 MPa. During the fitting procedure, it was found that the data of Michels and Goudekot [62] agree better with the new speed-of-sound measurements of this work than the data of Michels et al. [63] from 1959, which were the primary data of the EOS of Leachman et al. [7].

The measurements of Michels and Goudekot [62] cover a temperature range of 273 K to 424 K at pressures up to 301 MPa. The new EOS represents the data in the region of interest within 0.07 % and with an AARD of 0.021 %, and beyond that region within 0.3 %. The data of Michels et al. [63] range from 98 K to 424 K with pressures up to 300 MPa. Compared to the data of Michels and Goudekot [62], the data of Michels et al. [63] deviate further from the data of Jaeschke and Humphreys [55] and the gap widens with increasing pressure, cf. Fig. 4 ($T = 275\text{K}$, $T = 353\text{K}$) and Fig. 5. This trend continues for the entire temperature range.

It should be noted that almost all data sets deviate from each other at pressures higher than 20 MPa. The only exception is the data set of Wiebe and Gaddy [71], which agrees with the measurements of Michels and Goudekot [62] at pressures above 30 MPa, but is in better agreement with the data of Jaeschke and Humphreys [55] and Michels et al. [63] at lower pressures. The data of Michels et al. [63] are reproduced by the new EOS in the region of interest within 0.3 % and with an AARD of 0.062 %, and beyond that range within 1.3 %. The data of Wiebe and Gaddy [71] are represented within 0.05 % and the AARD is 0.025 %. Combined experimental uncertainties are not provided in the corresponding publications.

Considering the deviations of the reference data sets, the estimated uncertainty for the calculation of homogeneous density data with the new EOS at temperatures between 270 K and 355 K at pressures up to 30 MPa is 0.04 % although the stated experimental uncertainty is higher. This already conservative estimation can be made because the new speed-of-sound measurements of this work are consistent with the density data of Jaeschke and Humphreys [55] in the common temperature and pressure ranges and both the new EOS and the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] represent the data well within their estimated experimental uncertainty. The estimated uncertainty outside this range and in the region of interest at temperatures from 140 K to 370 K and pressures up to 100 MPa is 0.3 %. At temperatures beyond this range from 100 K to 425 K at pressures up to 300 MPa, the estimated uncertainty is 1.3 %.

4.3. Speed of sound

57 Speed-of-sound data were measured in the scope of this work at temperatures from 273 K to 323 K and pressures up to 100 MPa. Including these, 2373 experimental speed-of-sound data are now available in the literature, cf. Table 11. The total number of data points (N), the data points for the region of interest (N_{reg}), temperature and pressure range, and the AARD from the new EOS and the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] based on the region of interest are given. References with data located in the region of interest are highlighted with bold letters

Relative deviations of the speed-of-sound data from the new EOS are presented in Fig. 6 as a function of pressure in the temperature range from 273 K to 323 K at pressures up to 11 MPa and Fig. 7 presents the new measurements only, including the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] as dash-dotted curves for comparison. Carey et al. [72] measured speeds of sound in the largest temperature and pressure range within the region of interest. However, they did not report measurement uncertainties. The data are represented by the EOS within 1.7 % and an AARD of 0.42 %. Giacobbe [73] provides three measurements for pure hydrogen basically at one temperature and pressure. The largest deviation from the EOS is 0.32 % and the AARD is 0.19 %. The measurements of Hodge [75] were made on a sample of low but unquantified purity; the data have an offset of 5.0 % to 5.4 % from the EOS and are not considered further.

The newly measured data are mostly represented by the new EOS well within their experimental uncertainty. The data at pressures below 10 MPa, measured with the cylindrical resonator, have an experimental uncertainty of 0.04 %. The deviations of the cylindrical resonator data from the new EOS are smaller than the experimental uncertainty, except for two data points, cf. Fig. 7, and the AARD is 0.018 %. The EOS of

Table 12

Average absolute deviations (AAD) of data for the second ($B/(\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1})$) and third ($C/(10^3 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2})$) thermal virial coefficients for n -hydrogen calculated with the short EOS developed in this work. The AAD is based on the number of data points in the region of interest (N_{reg} , $140 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 370 \text{ K}$). For comparison, the same data were evaluated with the reference EOS of Leachman et al. [7].

Author	N	N_{reg}	$T_{\text{min}} - T_{\text{max}}$ K	AAD (Leachman et al. [7])	AAD (this work)
<i>Second thermal virial coefficient $B/(\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1})$</i>					
Bartlett et al. (1928) [49]	5	3	273–573	0.54	0.66
Beenakker et al. (1959) [79]	1	–	20–39	–	–
Cottrell et al. (1956) [80]	1	1	303.13	0.54	0.43
de Haas (1912) [52]	3	–	15–21	–	–
El Hadi et al. (1969) [81]	7	–	19–24	–	–
Garberoglio et al. (2012) [82]	33	8	15–2000	0.17	0.024
Gibby et al. (1929) [83]	7	4	298–449	0.093	0.16
Holborn & Otto (1925) [53]	8	5	90–474	4.1	4.3
Holborn & Otto (1926) [54]	1	–	65.26	–	–
Johnston et al. (1953) [57]	19	5	35–300	0.62	0.80
Kerl (1982) [84]	1	1	293.06	44.0	44.0
Knaap et al. (1962) [58]	24	–	13–66	–	–
Long & Brown (1937) [85]	7	–	20–47	–	–
Lopatinskii et al. (1991) [86]	2	2	293.14	0.96	1.1
Michels & Goudekete (1941) [62]	21	15	273–424	0.67	0.56
Michels et al. (1959) [63]	17	11	98–424	0.28	0.16
Michels et al. (1960) [87]	17	11	98–424	0.32	0.18
Mihara et al. (1977) [88]	3	3	298–349	0.22	0.16
Mueller et al. (1961) [89]	6	6	144–284	0.24	0.16
Nijhoff & Keesom (1927) [90]	8	3	24–374	0.3	0.19
Patkowski et al. (2008), PIMC [91]	17	8	50–600	0.15	0.031
Patkowski et al. (2008), Semiclassical [91]	19	8	15–600	0.06	0.12
Patkowski et al. (2008), Quantum [91]	19	8	15–600	0.069	0.093
Perez et al. (1980) [92]	5	2	299–500	0.32	0.21
Sakoda et al. (2012) [65]	8	3	353–474	0.32	0.013
Schramm et al. (1991) [93]	1	1	296.14	0.4	0.30
Scott (1929) [66]	1	1	298.14	0.062	0.17
Townend & Bhatt (1931) [67]	2	2	273–299	0.63	0.63
van Agt & Kamerlingh Onnes (1963) [68]	9	–	14–91	–	–
Varekamp & Beenakker (1959) [94]	9	–	15–21	–	–
Verschoye (1926) [70]	2	2	273–294	0.11	0.22
Wiebe & Gaddy (1938) [71]	6	4	273–574	0.54	0.59
Total	289	117	13–2000		
<i>Third thermal virial coefficient $C/(10^3 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2})$</i>					
Holborn & Otto (1925) [53]	5	3	90–274	0.24	0.21
Johnston et al. (1953) [57]	19	5	35–300	0.03	0.098
Michels & Goudekete (1941) [62]	21	15	273–424	0.43	0.38
Michels et al. (1959) [63]	17	11	98–424	0.11	0.057
Mihara et al. (1977) [88]	3	3	298–349	0.076	0.058
Sakoda et al. (2012) [65]	8	3	353–474	0.13	0.079
Scott (1929) [66]	1	1	298.14	0.26	0.32
Townend & Bhatt (1931) [67]	2	2	273–299	0.19	0.24
Verschoye (1926) [70]	2	2	273–294	0.031	0.086
Total	78	45	35–474		

Leachman et al. [7] represents the data within 0.13 % and with an AARD of 0.045 %. The deviation between the two EOS is smaller than 0.05 % at pressures below 2 MPa, although the deviation between the EOS for calculated ideal isobaric heat capacities is 0.2 % in the temperature range of measured speeds of sounds. The speeds of sound are over-predicted by the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] and the deviations to the experimental data become larger with increasing pressure and temperature. The new EOS represents these data with an AARD of 0.037 % and mostly within their experimental uncertainty of 0.05 % to 0.08 %. These data deviate further from the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] with an AARD of 0.22 %. The combined AARD of both measurement methods from the new EOS is 0.027 %.

Based on the experimental speed-of-sound data presented in this work, we estimate that speeds of sound calculated with the new EOS have a relative uncertainty of 0.05 % at temperatures from 273 K to 323 K and at pressures up to 10 MPa. At pressures up to 100 MPa in the same temperature range, the estimated uncertainty is 0.1 %. Uncertainties beyond the given ranges cannot be estimated.

4.4. Thermal virial coefficients

The virial coefficients characterize the intermolecular interaction in the vicinity of zero density. The second virial coefficient considers binary intermolecular interactions and the third virial coefficient the interactions between three molecules. There are 289 and 78 data available for the second and third thermal virial coefficients, respectively. The data are summarized in Table 12 with the overall number of data points (N), number of data points in the region of interest (N_{reg}), the temperature ranges, and the average absolute deviations AAD of the data sets in the region of interest from the new EOS as well as from the EOS of Leachman et al. [7]. References with data located in the region of interest are highlighted with bold letters.

Fig. 8 shows absolute deviations of the data from the new EOS for the (a) second and (b) third thermal virial coefficient and the absolute curve progression of the new EOS at two different scales, respectively (c to f). The absolute deviation is used for validation instead of the relative deviation because the zero-crossing of the virial coefficients causes large percentage deviations, rendering the relative approach less meaningful.

Fig. 8. Deviations of the a) second and b) third thermal virial coefficient data from the EOS of this work as a function of temperature. c), e) Second and d), f) third thermal virial coefficient as a function of temperature calculated from the new EOS and from the EOS of Leachman et al. [7]. Available literature data are included for comparison.

The data sets of Garberoglio et al. [82] and Patkowski et al. [91] are the most consistent among the second thermal virial coefficient data and cover a wider temperature range than the other references. The data of Garberoglio et al. [82] and the first data set of Patkowski et al. [91] were computed with a path-integral Monte Carlo (PIMC) approach. This method is believed to provide more accurate results for the second thermal virial coefficient compared to experimental measurements, provided that the underlying potential energy models used in the calculations are sufficiently accurate. The data set of Garberoglio et al. [82] covers a temperature range from 15 K to 2000 K. In the region of interest, the maximum deviation of the data from the new EOS is $0.04 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and the AAD is $0.02 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. Beyond the region of interest, the deviations remain within $0.1 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ at temperatures from 60 K to 450 K and $2 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ at temperatures from 35 K to 1000 K.

Patkowski et al. [91] determined second virial coefficient data with three approaches, namely PIMC, semiclassical approximation, and full quantum calculations. They all agree well with the data of Garberoglio et al. [82] in the region of interest, especially the PIMC data, which have a maximum deviation of $0.07 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and an AAD of $0.031 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ from the new EOS in the region of interest. Michels et al. [63,87], whose homogeneous density data were used for the development and validation of the new EOS, provided virial coefficient data as well. They cover the temperatures between 98 K and 424 K. Both data sets were computed from the same experimental density data [63] by extrapolation to zero density. In the region of interest, the new EOS reproduces the data of Michels et al. [63] within $0.4 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and an AAD of $0.16 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and the data of Michels et al. [87] within $0.4 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ with an AAD of $0.18 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. The two data sets show a

Fig. 9. p , ρ -diagrams and T , ρ -diagrams presenting the extrapolation behavior of the EOS of this work and of Leachman et al. [7]. Subplots a) and b) illustrate isotherms at temperatures from 14 K to 2400 K at pressures up to 10^4 MPa. Subplots c) and d) show isotherms from 14 K to 200 K at pressures up to 200 MPa. Subplots e) and f) show isobars from 0 MPa to 2 MPa at temperatures up to 45 K.

Fig. 10. Speed of sound as a function of temperature calculated with the new EOS (left) and of Leachman et al. [7] (right) at pressures up to 6 MPa.

different trend compared to the data of Patkowski et al. [91] and Garberoglio et al. [82], starting at lower values for the second thermal virial coefficient at lower temperatures and increasing with a steeper slope to higher values. Therefore, the data of Garberoglio et al. [82] are considered as reference for the uncertainty estimation of the new EOS. The estimated uncertainty of calculated second virial coefficient data is $0.05 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ at temperatures from 140 K to 370 K, beyond the region

of interest $0.1 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ at temperatures between 60 K and 450 K, and $2 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ beyond that region and within the temperature range from 35 K to 1000 K.

Data for the third thermal virial coefficient were used for validation only. Although the new EOS was not fitted to the second thermal virial coefficient data of Michels et al. [63], it represents the corresponding third thermal virial coefficient data in the region of interest, 140 K to

Fig. 11. Characteristic ideal curves calculated with the EOS of this work (top) and Leachman et al. [7] (bottom): Boyle curve (BL), ideal curve (ID), Joule-Thomson inversion curve (JT), and Joule inversion curve (JI), vapor pressure curve (p_v).

370 K, with a maximum deviation of $110 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2}$ and an AAD of $57 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2}$. The data of Mihara et al. [88] are in good agreement with the data of Michels et al. [63] and are reproduced with the new EOS within $93 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2}$ and an AAD of $58 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2}$. The new EOS is estimated to calculate third thermal virial coefficients in the region of interest with an uncertainty of $110 \text{ cm}^6 \cdot \text{mol}^{-2}$.

5. Physical behavior of the equation of state

The quality of an EOS is usually not only determined by the representation of the experimental data, but also by its physical behavior in regions where no experimental data are available. Due to its simplified functional form, the present EOS exhibits some shortcomings with respect to the extrapolation behavior, which the user should be aware of.

These limitations are shown in the following by evaluating the characteristic curves of selected thermodynamic properties.

Fig. 9 presents the pressure as function of temperature and density calculated with the EOS of this work and the one of Leachman et al. [7]. The isotherms are supposed to converge with increasing pressure but to never intersect. That is the case for the new EOS at temperatures up to 950 K highlighted in green as shown in the Fig. 9 a), which presents isotherms from 14 K to 2400 K. The isotherm at 1100 K highlighted in red intersects with the green line at $97 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$ and 4490 MPa. The isotherms bend unphysically with increasing temperature and density. On the other side, the new EOS exhibits reasonable behavior at very low temperatures where the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] shows intersections of the isotherms, e.g. the isotherm at 14 K highlighted in purple. For comparison, the mentioned isotherms are highlighted in Fig. 9 a) and b). Another criterion is the saddle point at the critical isotherm. Panels c) and d) illustrate isotherms up to 200 K and the panels e) and f) illustrate isobars up to 2 MPa. The vapor-liquid equilibrium was not considered when developing the new EOS, the two-phase region is far outside of the range of validity of the new EOS. Therefore, the predicted critical pressure is smaller than the real value. The critical isotherm does not exhibit a saddle point at the critical point. This also distorts the course of the rectilinear diameter. For comparison, the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] correctly represents the critical region. Again, the new EOS extrapolates to low temperatures physically correct.

In Fig. 10, the speed of sound is shown as a function of temperature along selected pressures. In general, the speed of sound is greater in the liquid phase than in the gaseous phase except at the critical point where the saturation curves merge in a minimum. The saturated liquid curve is supposed to have a negative slope and curvature while the vapor line has a positive slope until it reaches a maximum before merging into the saturated liquid curve. The new EOS complies with these conditions except for the curvature which is positive up to 50 K. At temperatures below 14 K, the new EOS exhibits a continuous curve progression while the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] bends unphysically. At supercritical states, the new EOS behaves correctly and similar to the EOS of Leachman et al. [7].

Another typical criterion for the evaluation of the extrapolation behavior of an EOS is the analysis of the characteristic ideal curves. They are defined as curves along which a property of a real fluid behaves like the corresponding property of the hypothetical ideal gas at the same temperature and density [95]. Evaluating the representation of the ideal curves is especially useful for fluids with limited data especially at high temperatures, pressures, and densities. The ideal curves were defined with their relation to the compressibility factor by Span and Wagner [96]. The curves are presented in Fig. 11 in terms of reduced pressure as function of the reduced temperature. Both EOS correctly represent the ideal curve (ID), Boyle curve (BL), and Joule-Thomson inversion curve (JT). The Joule inversion curve (JI) of the new EOS has an unphysical positive curvature at temperatures below 50 K and the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] cannot be evaluated at temperatures below 50 K.

6. Evaluation of the computational speed

A comparison between the computational speeds when evaluating the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] and of this work has been carried out with the test framework Catch2 written in the programming language C++ [97]. The speed test was performed with the Intel C++ Compiler in Microsoft Visual Studio Community 2019 for Windows 10 (64-bit) [98,99] on the CPU i5-9400. It was performed for pressure p , Helmholtz energy a , internal energy u , isochoric heat capacity c_v , and speed of sound w , as functions of the temperature T and density ρ . Since temperature and density are the independent variables of the Helmholtz energy, the thermodynamic properties can directly be evaluated without any iteration, which might falsify the results. The definitions of these properties and the corresponding relation to the reduced Helmholtz energy and its derivatives are provided in Table 13. The abbreviations of

the partial derivatives of the Helmholtz energy with respect to the reciprocal reduced temperature τ and reduced density δ are:

$$\alpha_\tau = \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} \right)_\delta \quad (20)$$

$$\alpha_\delta = \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \delta} \right)_\tau \quad (21)$$

$$\alpha_{\tau\tau} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \alpha}{\partial \tau^2} \right)_\delta \quad (22)$$

$$\alpha_{\delta\delta} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \alpha}{\partial \delta^2} \right)_\tau \quad (23)$$

$$\alpha_{\tau\delta} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \alpha}{\partial \tau \partial \delta} \right) \quad (24)$$

The tests were performed at the temperature $T = 150$ K and density $\rho = 20$ mol·dm⁻³. The resulting time measurement is the mean of 100 calculation repetitions. The results are given in Fig. 12 including the standard deviations. The new EOS is evaluated 6 to 8 times faster than the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] in the same framework. With more optimized programming schemes such as Horner's method [100], even higher calculation speeds can be achieved. The computation time of the speed of sound is greater than for other properties because more Helmholtz derivatives must be evaluated, cf. Eq. (32). Nevertheless, the ratio of the speed increase of the new EOS compared to the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] is similar for all properties.

Table 13

Definitions of the Helmholtz energy a , pressure p , internal energy u , isochoric heat capacity c_v , speed of sound w , and their relation to the reduced Helmholtz energy α and its derivatives.

Property	Relation to α and its derivatives
$p = -\left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial v}\right)_\tau$ (25)	$\frac{p}{\rho RT} = 1 + \delta \alpha'_\delta$ (26)
$u = a + Ts$ (27)	$\frac{u}{RT} = \tau(\alpha'_\tau + \alpha'_\delta)$ (28)
$c_v = \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial T}\right)_v$ (29)	$\frac{c_v}{R} = -\tau^2(\alpha''_{\tau\tau} + \alpha''_{\delta\delta})$ (30)
$w = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho}\right)_s}$ (31)	$\frac{w^2}{RT} = 1 + 2\delta \alpha'_\delta + \delta^2 \alpha''_{\delta\delta} - \frac{(1 + \delta \alpha'_\tau - \delta \tau \alpha'_{\tau\delta})^2}{\tau^2(\alpha''_{\tau\tau} + \alpha''_{\delta\delta})}$ (32)

Fig. 12. Computational time t of the EOS of Leachman et al. [7] and this work for calculated pressure p , Helmholtz energy a , internal energy u , isochoric heat capacity c_v , and speed of sound w . The time t_w given by the y-axis on the right applies to the speed of sound only. The speed test was performed at $T = 150$ K and $\rho = 20$ mol·dm⁻³. The mean values and standard deviations from 100 calculations are shown.

7. Conclusion

The speed of sound was measured in n -hydrogen at 273 K, 298 K, and 323 K with pressures up to 100 MPa. A cylindrical resonator was used at pressures from 1 MPa to 10 MPa and the dual-path pulse-echo technique was used at pressures from 20 MPa to 100 MPa. The estimated experimental uncertainty for the speed-of-sound measurements is between 0.04 % to 0.08 % ($k = 2$). The two different techniques were used due to the challengingly high speed of sound in hydrogen and low acoustic impedance compared to other gases. Combining these two techniques allowed to cover the whole pressure range from 1 MPa to 100 MPa.

Based on these measurements and additional literature data, a new EOS for n -hydrogen was developed for the temperature range from 140 K to 370 K and pressures up to 100 MPa. It is explicit in the reduced Helmholtz energy with the independent variables temperature and density. Its form is simplified to enable a fast computation time, leading to computation times 6 to 8 times faster than the EOS by Leachman et al. [7]. The ideal part consists of 5 polynomial terms and the residual part comprises 9 polynomial terms.

The equation parameters were adjusted to data computed from ab initio data for isobaric heat capacities of the ideal gas and second thermal virial coefficients and to experimental data for homogeneous densities, second thermal virial coefficients, and the speeds of sound measured in this work. Third virial coefficient data were used for comparison.

The estimated relative uncertainty of ideal isobaric heat capacities calculated with the new EOS in the temperature range from 140 K to 540 K is 0.2 % and outside this range 1 % from 85 K to 650 K. The relative uncertainty of densities calculated with the new EOS is estimated to be within 0.04 % at temperatures from 270 K and 355 K and pressures up to 30 MPa. Outside this range, the estimated uncertainty is 0.3 % at temperatures from 140 K to 370 K at pressures up to 100 MPa. Beyond this range, the estimated uncertainty is 1.3 % at temperatures from 100 K to 425 K at pressures up to 300 MPa. Based on the new speed-of-sound measurements, the relative uncertainty for speeds of sound at temperatures from 273 K to 323 K with pressures up to 10 MPa is estimated to be 0.05 %. At pressures up to 100 MPa in the same temperature range, the estimated uncertainty is 0.1 %. It should be noted that uncertainties beyond the given ranges cannot be estimated. Calculated second thermal virial coefficient data are estimated to have an uncertainty of 0.05 cm³·mol⁻¹ at temperatures from 140 K and 370 K, 0.1 cm³·mol⁻¹ at temperatures between 60 K and 450 K, and beyond that region 2 cm³·mol⁻¹ at temperatures from 35 K to 1000 K. The estimated uncertainty for the third thermal virial coefficient at temperatures from 140 K to 370 K is 110 cm⁶·mol⁻². Although the EOS exhibits a reasonable extrapolation behavior, calculations beyond the specified temperature and pressure ranges exhibit greater deviations from the EOS of Leachman et al. [7], which was fitted to the entire available experimental database.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tan-Trieu-Giang Nguyen: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Carsten Wedler:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sven Pohl:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology. **Dan Penn:** Validation, Investigation. **Roland Span:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **J.P. Martin Trusler:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Monika Thol:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal

relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Tan-Trieu-Giang Nguyen reports financial support was provided by EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research. Roland Span reports financial support was provided by European Research Council. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Most data can be made available on request, with the exception of data for which the authors do not have permission to share.

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